

Engineering Education Active Learning Maturity Model: a Conceptual Framework

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Abstract

Over the past few decades, the Engineering Education field has undergone a transformation, driven especially by technological advancements and 21st century student's characteristics. The emergence of publications proposing characteristics desired for the "21st century engineer", changes in the accreditation criteria of Engineering courses, several examples of changes in the curricula of Engineering courses throughout the world and the emergence of global initiatives for the modernization of engineering education, such as the CDIO, are the new reality of Engineering Education. In the transformation described, there is consensus in the literature about the need to focus on student learning and to stimulate student engagement. These two aspects are related to the adoption of Active Learning, a growing approach in Engineering courses around the world. Regardless of its popularity, there is no adequate way to evaluate the maturity of adoption of Active Learning in what concerns an institution, a program, or a course. This paper proposes a framework to evaluate the maturity of adoption of Active Learning by a specific course and, because of its aggregation, by a program or institution. The paper presents a literature review that allows identifying its Key Success Factors and the foundations of the maturity model, culminating in the proposed model. The next steps for the construction and validation of this maturity model are presented. In addition to these steps, possible future research and the main challenges identified are addressed.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Conference Information; Project Approaches.

1 Introduction

Since the beginning of the second half of the 20th century, the world has undergone technological changes that have impacted various fields of knowledge. Since the release of the first personal computers, the capacity and speed of data processing have increased exponentially and this has led to a transformation of people, which directly impacted the world of education in general, and the Engineering Education field specifically (Beanland & Hadgraft, 2013; Graham, 2018).

In the Engineering Education field, it is possible to identify several movements with the objective of modernizing programs and teaching process, such as the CDIO initiative (Crawley, Malmqvist, Östlund, Brodeur, & Edström, 2014), the change in ABET's accreditation criteria (called EC2000) (Lattuca, Terenzini, & Volkwein, 2006), in addition to institutions with proposals totally different from the traditional model of the 20th century, such as Olin College (Goldberg & Somerville, 2014) and Aalborg University (Mohd-yusof, Arsat, Borhan, Graaff, & Kolmos, 2013).

With this transformation taking place, one of the main recommendations is to place the student at the center of the learning process. This trend has enhanced the use of Active Learning, a research and practical field that has significantly grown over the last decade. Despite such growth, the literature still lacks a framework to help teachers and administrators evaluate the maturity of adoption of active learning initiatives. Such initiatives can be limited to a specific course or be as general as to embrace the whole educational institution. This work will propose a conceptual model that allows evaluating Active Learning initiatives at the level of a specific course, as this seems logically to be the first step towards a more general and comprehensive model that can evaluate institutions.

2 Methodology

The study begins with a literature review, looking for publications that deal with Key Success Factors (KSF) for the implementation of Active Learning and its variations in Higher Education Institutions (HEI). This review was based on databases Scopus and Web of Science, using keywords related with “active learning” and “engineering education”.

After the selection of publications dealing with this topic, a detailed survey of the identified KSF was carried out, with the aid of the MaxQDA® tool. The research procedures or activities are presented in Figure .

Then, the identified KSFs were consolidated, to group similar items and avoid duplication. After that, each factor had an assumed definition, based on the occurrences found in the literature. The next step was to define the relevant constructs for each factor. And for each construct, the variables that will be used for its measurement.

Figure 1. Research procedures

3 Results and discussion

As a result, Engineering Education Active Learning Maturity Model (EEALMM) with 4 levels is showed in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Engineering Education Active Learning Maturity Model (4 levels)

After literature review, 31 works were selected. These works, after consolidation, provided 14 key success factors divided into 5 dimensions, as follows:

- Quality of content (Artifacts, Student assessment and Learning facilitation),
- Organizational environment (Culture, Policy, Student feedback and Instructional design),
- Organizational structure (Classrooms and Technology),
- Professor/instructor (Knowledge, Skills and Attitude), and
- Interactions (Between students and With instructors).

For each KSF, the related constructs were proposed and, for each construct, the variables that will be measured. Each dimension will be detailed in next sections.

3.1 Quality of content

This dimension concentrates the factors related to the core of the learning process, such as the quality of the problems, projects or cases studied (artifacts), the level of difficulty required from the students, whether the activities facilitate learning and whether the evaluation criteria are clear and consistent. The three KSF are detailed below.

3.1.1 Artifacts

Course artifacts should:

- engage students with real-life problems and active experiences (Chen, Bastedo, & Howard, 2018),
- provide students with a variety of additional instructional resources, such as simulations, case studies, videos, and demonstrations (Chen et al., 2018),
- be suitable to achieve different targets including the support of the students' learning process and establishing learning outcomes requirements (Mughrabi & Jaeger, 2016),
- be clearly written, in the right length, useful, flexible, and provide appropriate degree of breath (Shee & Wang, 2008),
- have suitable intellectual challenge (Hegarty & Thompson, 2019; Kuh, 2001; Tomlinson, Evans, & Muijs Daniel, 2015; Zepke & Leach, 2010; Zepke, Leach, & Butler, 2010), and
- begin with an explanation of its purpose (Bacon & Stewart, 2019; DeMonbrun et al., 2017; Donohue & Richards, 2009).

3.1.2 Student Assessment

Student assessment needs to be clear, concise, and consistent. This involves instructions, assignments, assessments, due dates, course pages, and office hours (Chen et al., 2018). Furthermore, criteria for success must be communicated clearly and monitored (Chapman, 2003; Cochrane & Antonczak, 2015; Hattie & Donoghue, 2016; Hegarty & Thompson, 2019; Rutherford, 2010; Tarantino, McDonough, & Hua, 2013; Zepke & Leach, 2010).

3.1.3 Learning Facilitation

Learning facilitation includes the preparation of students to conduct activities and tasks required in addition to activities related to the facilitator guiding the learning process of the students (Mughrabi & Jaeger, 2016). Includes also regular opportunities for formative feedback from professor (Cochrane & Antonczak, 2015; Hegarty & Thompson, 2019; Mesquita et al., 2015; Tarantino et al., 2013; Zepke & Leach, 2010; Zepke et al., 2010).

Table shows the constructs and variables of each KSF defined above.

Table 1. Constructs and variables of Quality of content

Key Success Factor	Construct	Variables
Artifacts	Use of real-life problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of course content based on real-life problems
	Application of active experiments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of classes using active methods • Students' perception of hands-on activities
	Variety of instructional resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantity of instructional resources used • % of classes using resources other than the board or projector • Students' perception of the use of various resources
	Adequacy to Learning Outcomes (LO)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of classes linked directly to an LO • Students' perception of reaching an LO
	Suitability of intellectual challenge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students' perception of the level of difficulty presented
	Clarity in writing of course activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students' perception of the clarity used
	Size of course activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students' perception of size
	Explanation of purpose of course activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students' perception of clarity in the purpose of the activities • % of activities in which the purpose is explained to students
Student Assessment	Clearness of assessment methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perception of students on the clarity of assessment methods • Are the assessment methods defined in advance? • % of activities that have defined what is expected of the student
	Clearness of criteria for success	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perception of students on the clarity of success criteria • Are the success criteria defined in advance?
	Communications with students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is information about assessment methods and success criteria made available before (or at the beginning of) the course? • Students' perception of communication of assessment methods and success criteria
Learning Facilitation	Preparation of students to conduct activities required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of activities flagged as supporting another activity • Students' perception of the existing preparation for conducting activities • Students' perception of the teacher's performance as a facilitator • Intensity of the participation of monitors or auxiliary teachers during the course
	Formative feedback from teacher	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of activities where there is formative feedback from the teacher • Students' perception of the intensity of support received via formative feedback

3.2 Organizational environment

The factors of this dimension represent abstract aspects of the institution, such as culture, policy, and the practice of collecting feedback from students. These factors have their constructs and variables presented in Table 2.

3.2.1 Culture

Organizational culture is a set of values systems followed by members of an organization as guidelines for behaviour and solving the problems that occur in the organization (Priatna, Maylawati, Sugilar, & Ramdhani, 2020).

3.2.2 Policy

Organization policy is a set of program plans, activities and actions that allows to predict how the organization works and how a problem would be solved (Priatna et al., 2020). Once time is needed to prepare the activities, teachers must have it for implementing something new in their classes (Hernández-de-Menéndez, Vallejo Guevara, Tudón Martínez, Hernández Alcántara, & Morales-Menendez, 2019).

3.2.3 Student feedback

Act of collect feedback from students (DeMonbrun et al., 2017; Francoise, Benay, Kennedy, Semsar, & Bentley, Francoise Judith Benay; Kennedy, Sarah; Semsar, 2011; Yadav, Subedi, Lundeborg, & Bunting, 2011).

3.2.4 Instructional Design

Structure and coherence of the curriculum and the learning material (Brophy, 1999; Paechter, Maier, & Macher, 2010).

Table 2. Constructs and variables of Organization environment

Key Success Factor	Construct	Variables
Culture	Acceptance of changes by the organization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ease of approval of pedagogical changes Ease of approval of administrative changes
	Behaviour alignment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clarity of expected behaviours Existence (or maturity) of behavioural guidelines
	Ability to solve problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perception of the speed with which problems are solved Perception of transparency in problem solving
	Defining rules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Existence (or maturity) of a code of ethics
	Adequacy to the rules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perception of the existence of punishments for those who violate certain rules
Policy	Organizational support for the preparation of activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perception of the existence of time available for planning new activities % average of teachers' time in classroom activities % average of teachers' time in administrative activities Average amount of administrative functions performed by teachers Perception of the availability of auxiliary resources for the preparation of activities
	Adequacy of pedagogical plans	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perception of the adequacy of existing teaching plans to the use of AL
Student feedback	Process of collect	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Existence (or maturity) of the process of receiving feedback from students
	Proper use of feedback collected from students	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perception of students on the fulfilment of their placements in feedbacks Number of objective actions resulting from student feedback in the last years
	Quality of the feedback collected	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Is feedback anonymous? Is the collection in person or remote? Perception of students about the ease of the process of giving feedback
Instructional design	Structure of the curriculum	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Perception about the adequacy of the curriculum to the needs of the course
	Coherence of the curriculum and the learning material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Student perception of the alignment of the curriculum with the course material

3.3 Organizational structure

This dimension groups the factors that represent the structure that the organization makes available for the functioning of the activities. Table 3 shows the constructs and variables of each KSF.

3.3.1 Classrooms

Classrooms designed for improve active learning experience (Park & Choi, 2014) and equipped with technologies to enhance student learning and support teaching innovation (Charles, Whittaker, Dugdale, & Guillemette, 2015; Chiu & Cheng, 2017; Chiu, Lai, Fan, & Cheng, 2015; Dori & Belcher, 2005; Soderdahl, 2011).

3.3.2 Technology

Availability, reliability, accessibility, usability of devices, Internet (Wi-Fi), learning support. Inclusive learning environment (AUSSE, 2010; Hegarty & Thompson, 2019; Kuh, 2001; Tarantino et al., 2013).

Table 3. Constructs and variables of Organization structure

Key Success Factor	Construct	Variables
Classrooms	Classrooms designed for improve active learning experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existence of classrooms for Active Learning • Classroom availability for Active Learning • % of activities performed in an environment suitable for Active Learning
	Classrooms equipped with technologies to enhance student learning and support teaching innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existence of classrooms equipped with multimedia devices and / or laboratories • Availability of classrooms equipped with multimedia devices and / or laboratories • % of activities performed in a technologically appropriate environment
Technology	Availability of technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of multimedia devices • Internet availability on campus • Availability of e-learning system
	Reliability of technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reliability of multimedia devices • On-campus internet reliability • Reliability of e-learning system
	Accessibility of technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessibility of multimedia devices • On-campus internet accessibility • Accessibility of e-learning system
	Usability of technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usability of multimedia devices • Campus internet usability • Usability of e-learning system

3.4 Professor / instructor / teacher

The teacher is the main single actor in a successfully implementation of Active Learning. This dimension group factors that represents their knowledge, skills, and attitude to carry out education innovation. Table 4 shows constructs and variables of each KSF.

3.4.1 Knowledge

Knowledge is a combination of framed experience, values and contextual information that provides an environment for evaluating and incorporating new experiences (Priatna et al., 2020).

3.4.2 Skills

Skills are the ability to use reason, thoughts, ideas and creativity in doing, changing, or making things more meaningful so as to produce a value from the results of the work. (Priatna et al., 2020).

3.4.3 Attitude

Attitude is essentially a human activity, which has a very broad range, including walking, talking, acting, thinking, perception, and emotions (Priatna et al., 2020).

Table 4. Constructs and variables of dimension Professor

Key Success Factor	Construct	Variables
Knowledge	Experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Activity time as a teacher • Highest academic title • Time since the highest titration
	Contextual information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Level of knowledge about Active Learning
Skills	Skills about Active Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amount of participation in Active Learning events • Number of books read on Active Learning • Amount of Active Learning techniques over which you have mastery
	Skills about educational innovations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amount of participation in events on educational innovations • Number of books read on educational innovations
Attitude	Willingness to adopt Active Learning techniques	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative perception of disposition • Number of periods in which adoption was attempted • Number of subjects in which adoption was attempted • Time since last adoption attempt
	Demography	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age • Current position • Study area

3.5 Interactions

Placing students at the centre of the learning process requires them to step out of the role of recipients of information and become active agents. The interaction between students and between them and teachers allows this transition to happen. Table 5 shows constructs and variables of each factor.

3.5.1 Between students

Opportunities for students to work together and obtain peer feedback included in the learning design (Hegarty & Thompson, 2019).

3.5.2 With instructors

Interaction between students and instructor supports knowledge construction, motivation, and the establishment of a social relationship (Paechter et al., 2010).

Table 5. Constructs and variables of dimension Interaction facilitation

Key Success Factor	Construct	Variables
Between students	Interactions in general	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantity of work / projects carried out in group in the course • % of the grade of the discipline from group work
	Online collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of remote meetings with other students throughout the course • Number of online presentations made by the student with assistance from other students
	Face-to-face collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of face-to-face meetings with other students throughout the course • Number of face-to-face presentations made by the student with the assistance of other students
With instructors	Interactions students/professors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of orientation meetings throughout the course • Number of meetings to monitor projects throughout the course

4 Conclusion

With the advances made in the Engineering Education field in recent years, it has become clear that institutions increasingly need to place the student at the centre of the learning process. As a result, the use of Active Learning has been boosted and has expanded worldwide.

However, the lack of a way of measuring maturity in this regard is a point that hinders evolution. This study proposed a framework to evaluate the maturity of adoption of Active Learning by a specific course. The variables described here can serve as a checklist to teachers adopting active learning and as a metric to evaluate the comprehensiveness and quality of existing initiatives.

As future work, we will: (i) define the measurement method and the scale of each variable; (ii) determine the weights of each KSF in their respective dimensions; (ii) validate the framework as a whole with an international panel of experts; and (iii) test the framework to evaluate the maturity of real cases, which will allow qualitative and quantitative analyses.

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